

Hemodynamic Collapse Due to Leiomyosarcoma: Intracardiac Obstruction as a Trigger for Multiorgan Dysfunction

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ABSTRACT

We present a malignant intracardiac tumor causing hemodynamic collapse and multiorgan dysfunction. The uncommon clinical presentation included progressive dyspnea associated with recurrent pleural effusions, initially approached as rheumatologic disease due to renal failure, serositis, anemia, and thrombocytopenia. The patient experienced positional syncope, biventricular cardiogenic shock, severe jugular distension, collateral circulation, edema, and pulmonary congestion requiring advanced life support. Echocardiography revealed a myxoid mass in the left atrium protruding through the mitral valve, significantly affecting cardiac function. Surgical resection achieved temporary remission, with histopathology confirming epithelioid leiomyosarcoma. However, prognosis remains poor due to high recurrence and therapeutic resistance.

KEYWORDS: Leiomyosarcoma, Multiorgan Dysfunction, Intracardiac, Tumor, Obstruction

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I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiac masses are certainly a rare pathology. Evaluation begins by ruling out valve vegetations and thrombi, which are the most common entities. Following these, cardiac tumors, which may be classified as primary or secondary, should be considered. Among cardiac tumors, secondary tumors resulting from metastatic dissemination are the next most frequent category. Primary cardiac tumors are infrequent and can further be subdivided into benign and malignant. Benign primary cardiac tumors represent approximately 80% of cases; of these, about 80% in adults are attributed to myxomas, with the remaining 20% comprising a mix of lipomas, fibromas, hemangiomas, and other entities. Only around 15% of primary cardiac tumors are malignant, with angiosarcomas being the most common type. Other sarcomas, such as leiomyosarcoma, synovial sarcoma, osteosarcoma, fibrosarcoma, myxoid sarcoma, liposarcoma, neurofibrosarcoma, among others, follow in frequency. (1).

II. CLINICAL CASE

A 41-year-old female with a two-year history of type 2 diabetes managed with biguanides. She denies allergies, recent infections, travel history, or other relevant cardiovascular antecedents.

Her condition began with dyspnea upon major exertion, progressively worsening until it became incapacitating. Initial evaluation revealed bilateral pleural effusion on chest radiography, managed with loop diuretics, and upon symptom resolution.

Four months later, she returned due to dyspnea occurring with minimal exertion. A study protocol was initiated to investigate recurrent pleural effusions, including a rheumatological panel due to suspected autoimmune disease and initiating pulse steroid. Empirical antibiotic therapy with a carbapenem was initiated for suspected sepsis. Additionally, bicytopenia was noted, particularly severe thrombocytopenia. Hematology was consulted, suspecting an

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autoimmune etiology, and began treatment with intravenous immunoglobulin G, resulting in partial platelet response.

During hospitalization and ongoing treatment, she experienced syncope triggered by positional changes, fully recovering upon elevation of the lower limbs, but with sudden hemodynamic deterioration. Cardiac auscultation revealed low-intensity rhythmic heart sounds, sinus tachycardia, and a grade II/IV mid-to-late diastolic murmur best heard at the mitral area (Figure 1). She required supplemental oxygen, with adequate respiratory movements, no accessory muscle use, marked by severe collateral venous circulation around the clavicular region, and grade 4 jugular venous distension.

Due to hemodynamic instability, dual vasopressor therapy was initiated. An echocardiographic evaluation was performed, revealing a myxoid mass occupying the left atrium and protruding through the mitral valve toward the mid-segment of the left ventricle, significantly compromising hemodynamics. A protocol was initiated to address this intracardiac mass, highly suggestive of a myxoma due to its location (Figure 2)

Figure 1. 12-lead ECG prior to mass resection.

A. Laboratory

The patient's laboratory profile shows significant multiorgan dysfunction, evidenced by severe thrombocytopenia (4000 μ L) and anemia (8 g dL), likely secondary to an autoimmune disease given the positive Coombs test. The elevation of cardiac enzymes, with CK-MB at 49 U/L, indicates cardiac involvement. At the hepatic level, increased ALT (2417 U/L), bilirubin (2.24 mg dL), and LDH (2146 U/L) suggest hepatocellular damage, consistent with hepatic congestion. Additionally, severe hyponatremia may be related to volume overload. The elevation of tumor markers Ca-125 (413 U/mL) and Ca 19-9 (41 U/mL) raises suspicion of an underlying neoplastic process, although they are not definitive for diagnosis. Overall, these findings point to progressive multiorgan failure of an undetermined etiology (Table1).

(TABLE 1) Key Laboratory Finding

Parameter	Result	Parameter	Result
Hemoglobin	8.00 g/dL	Procalcitonin	1.31 ng/mL
Platelets	4000 / μ L	Glucose	190 mg/dL
Sodium	121 mmol/L	Urea	102 mg/dL
ALT	2417 U/L	Ca-125	413 U/mL
LDH	2146 U/L	Ca 19-9	41.04 U/mL
Bilirubin (Total)	5.85 mg/dL	Total Proteins	5.6 g/dL
CK-MB	43 U/L	Albumin	3.5 g/dL
Troponin	0.032 ng/mL		

B. Transthoracic Echocardiogram

Left atrial tumor measuring 6.84 \times 3.46 cm protruding through the mitral valve into the mid third of the left ventricle, causing significant hemodynamic compromise. Heart failure with reduced left ventricular ejection fraction 30 percent. Pericardial effusion with maximal leaf separation of 19 mm.

Figure 2. (A) Cardiac mass in the atrium during systole. (B) Cardiac mass with mitral protrusion during diastole (reducing left ventricular filling).

TAPSE: 19 mm (Figure 2).

C. Cardiac CT Angiography

Heterogeneous, solid appearing lesion in left atrium measuring 35 \times 57 mm, lobulated, hypodense, with slight central contrast enhancement, suggestive of malignant etiology. Completely occupies the right inferior pulmonary vein (Figures 3, 4).

Figure 3. CT Angiography images. At the top, from left to right, short-axis, four-chamber, and three-chamber views demonstrate a solid-appearing, lobulated, hypodense mass in the left atrium measuring 35 × 57 mm, with slight central contrast enhancement suggestive of malignancy. At the bottom, images show that the mass completely occupies the right inferior pulmonary vein.

D. Biopsy (Surgical resection)

- Excision of atrial mass originating from right inferior pulmonary vein, firm consistency, yellow-colored, lobulated, completely occluding its lumen (100% obstruction).(Figure 5)
- Pathology received 36 grams of smooth, lobulated, yellow tissue measuring 8 × 4 × 3 cm in total; upon sectioning, tissue appeared pale yellow with cystic and gelatinous areas.

Figure 4. CT Angiography: 3D reconstructions demonstrating the large filling defect caused by the mass in the left atrium and the right inferior pulmonary vein.

Figure 5. Cardiac mass protruding through the mitral valve visualized during open-heart surgery.

E. Histopathological Examination

- Malignant myxoid mesenchymal neoplasm.

F. Immunohistochemistry

Epithelioid leiomyosarcoma, Desmin: strongly positive (3+) in 100% of cells, ERG: negative, Actin: negative, CD31: negative (positive in superficial thrombus), S100: negative, Myogenin: negative, MyoD1: negative neoplasm.

G. Head CT Scan (non-contrast)

Nodular, hypodense, space-occupying lesion in the right parietal lobe with slightly defined margins and attenuation values of 16-18 HU, measuring 30 × 31 × 29 mm. Associated perilesional edema causing obliteration of the posterior horn of the ipsilateral lateral ventricle. After intravenous contrast administration, ring enhancement up to 45 HU is observed.

Upon documenting the intracardiac lesion, the patient was admitted to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) for monitoring and cardiovascular support. Following a multidisciplinary meeting, the surgical plan was defined as a median sternotomy approach with pericardial marsupialization supported by cardiopulmonary bypass. Both venae cavae were cannulated and cinched, followed by a right atriotomy and atrial septostomy, allowing visualization of a firm, lobulated, yellow-colored mass originating from the right inferior pulmonary vein, completely obstructing its lumen. (Figure 5). The mass was subsequently excised, and closure of the atrial septum and right atrium was performed. After purging the left heart chambers, the patient was successfully weaned off bypass on the first attempt. An epicardial pacemaker lead was placed in the right ventricle, followed by chest closure. In the immediate postoperative period, the patient remained dependent on vasopressors, which were gradually tapered until fully discontinued, contributing to the resolution of multiorgan failure.

During hospitalization, due to a systemic inflammatory response, thrombocytopenia, anemia suggestive of autoimmune etiology, and low complement levels,

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rheumatological biomarker studies were performed but yielded non-significant results.

Additionally, despite recognizing the limited diagnostic value of tumor markers for this condition, elevated levels of tumor markers (such as Ca-125 and Ca 19-9 antigens) were noted, raising suspicion of a possible neoplastic process beyond an autoimmune origin.

The histopathological examination revealed a malignant myxoid mesenchymal neoplasm, with immunohistochemistry confirming epithelioid leiomyosarcoma: strongly positive desmin (3+) in 100% of cells; negative ERG, actin, CD31 (positive only in superficial thrombus), s100, myogenin, and MyoD1.

Within two months of histopathological diagnosis, the patient experienced rapid clinical deterioration due to aggressively spreading metastatic lesions, leading to enlargement of the abdominal mass (Figure 6) and increased intracranial pressure caused by multiple cerebral lesions accompanied by perilesional edema. These lesions compromised autonomic functions, preventing the initiation of palliative treatment and resulting in the patient's rapid demise.

The performed surgical treatment aimed to achieve both potential curative and palliative outcomes; however, for curative intent, evidence of the absence of metastatic disease was essential.

Nevertheless, surgical protocols for this type of neoplasm are not well established due to limited clinical experience, and mortality is intrinsically linked to the natural history of the disease.

DISCUSSION

Leiomyosarcomas are malignant neoplasms arising from smooth muscle tissue, potentially originating wherever smooth muscle is found. Common sites of presentation include the uterus, retroperitoneum, gastrointestinal tract, and vascular structures. (2) Leiomyosarcomas are extremely rare, accounting for approximately 8% of soft tissue sarcomas and ranking as the third most common type of sarcoma. Intracardiac sarcomas originating from major vessels are particularly rare, with pulmonary artery involvement reported at an incidence of 0.001%–0.03%. Primary sarcomas originating from pulmonary veins are exceptionally rare, with only around 30 cases documented, predominantly involving the right superior pulmonary vein extending into the left atrium; among these, leiomyosarcoma is the most common histologic type. In the presented clinical case, not only was there atrial involvement, but significant hemodynamic instability occurred due to obstruction of left ventricular filling caused by the tumor protruding through the mitral valve. (2,3) Clinical manifestations in these patients are usually nonspecific and depend entirely on the tumor's location and extent. Symptoms may range from superior vena cava syndrome, cough, exertional dyspnea, pain, weight loss, and signs suggestive of thromboembolism or heart failure, to

cardiac tamponade, syncope, and even sudden cardiac death. Clinical experience and a thorough diagnostic approach are essential for timely and appropriate therapeutic intervention. (4,5) Management of this pathology requires a multidisciplinary approach with the primary goal being radical surgical resection to ensure negative margins. Additionally, in cases of metastatic disease, adjuvant chemotherapy can be considered to improve patient survival. (9) Documented cardiac complications in the postoperative period include heart failure, arrhythmias, atrioventricular block, and phrenic nerve paralysis. The medical literature reports a high incidence of distant metastasis. Surgical resection aims to overcome the patient's critical phase; as reported in this case, it also seeks to alleviate symptoms and provide improved quality of life. (8) The prognosis primarily depends on tumor location, mitotic index, and the degree of differentiation. Given that the surgical goal involves radical resection within vital cardiac structures, the risk of recurrence is as high as 52%. (6) Recurrences are frequent, with reported survival rates ranging from 31% to 66.7% at 5 years following complete macroscopic resection. In contrast, survival rates drop to 0% at 5 years when resection margins remain positive for tumor. Thus, the initial surgical findings and outcomes are critical determinants for survival. (5) Other factors influencing long-term survival include left-sided cardiac location, absence of necrotic areas within the tumor section, and absence of distant metastases. (7)

CONCLUSIONS

Primary malignant intracardiac tumors represent a significant diagnostic challenge due to their rarity and aggressiveness. Their detection would not be feasible without timely, experienced, and multidisciplinary intervention. Sarcomas—particularly leiomyosarcomas—tend to exhibit inherently aggressive and invasive behavior. Once identified, radical surgical and medical interventions are often necessary; however, the likelihood of achieving malignancy remission remains low. In the present case, therapeutic options are further limited by the involvement of vital cardiac structures, resulting in high mortality and a poor short-term prognosis.

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